

IMPACT OF FREE AND COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON SCHOOL ENROLLMENT IN SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE (2015-2025)

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ABSTRACT

Education is a major investment in human capital development, and as such, the provision of quality education in Akwa Ibom State has been a matter of major concern by different administrations, which necessitated the introduction of the free and compulsory education system in Akwa Ibom State. With all the state Government efforts in boosting the educational system in the state, there are some problems, such as low enrollment rates, high dropout rates, inadequate infrastructure, low school performance, teacher quality, assessment and evaluation, cultural and social factors, policy implementation, suboptimal learning outcomes, including quality of education, and socioeconomic factors. The study examined free and compulsory education, as well as human capital development, in selected secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The descriptive research design was used with a study population of 461,615, representing the total number of students enrolled in free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used as a method of data analysis. From the findings of the study, it was revealed, among others, that there is a positive and statistically significant relationship between free and compulsory education and students' enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings, the study recommended, amongst others, that the Akwa Ibom State Government should work hand in hand with different ministry of education in formulating policies to encourage students' enrollment

Keywords: Education, School enrollment, and Secondary School

INTRODUCTION

Formal education is regarded as one of the ways of developing sound human capital for the growth and development of any nation. According to the World Bank (2004),

education is a major investment in human capital development, and it plays a crucial role in long-term productivity and growth at both micro and macro levels (Kingdom, 2014). Thus, provision of quality education in Akwa Ibom State in particular, and Nigeria in general has been a matter of public discourse at all levels. This approach of human capital development is achieved through the utilisation of sound educational resources. Educational resources are the human and technical capitals used in the attainment of educational goals and objectives. Presently, the objective of the free and compulsory education programme is to provide education (both in quality and quantity) to all the residents within the boundaries of the state, irrespective of the state of origin, to eradicate illiteracy. Provision of quality education has been ranked as the best legacy any reliable leader, government or parent could leave for her/his people because it determines the standard of growth achieved. No wonder as far back as 1981, the Federal Government of Nigeria stated that education has been adopted as an instrument par excellence for effective national development (Udoh, 2008).

As noted by Kodde, (2022), the benefits of education do not only include freedom from ignorance and superstitious beliefs, it also inculcate freedom of the mind for quicker perception of issues; inspire the spirit of enquiry and experimentation; and stimulate creativity and innovation. The provision of quality free and compulsory education entails the removal of every socio-cultural impediment to education. It is backed up by the establishment of various kinds of schools and the expansion of the school curriculum to make each child develop according to his or her ability, age and interest. Such a programme is supported with the establishment and provision of library facilities, technical and vocational equipment, recruitment and retention of qualified and adequate manpower, free tuition, free feeding, free books, free accommodation, free transportation, and uniform and other personal needs of the learners. The provision of education for the citizens is a constitutional right that should not be infringed. Meanwhile, education in Nigeria has been regarded to be free and compulsory up to the senior secondary level, with substantial subsidisation at the tertiary level. Right from 1999, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Scheme was launched to provide free and compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian of school-going age. This is also backed by section 18(3) of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria that reiterates the mandate of the government to eradicate illiteracy by providing free, compulsory and universal primary education; free secondary education; and free adult literacy programme (Denga, 2016).

The implementation of the free and compulsory education in the State witnessed tremendous changes in enrollment at both the primary and secondary levels-an increase in both male and female enrollments. The implementation of free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State has recorded a high degree of positive comments from people within and outside the state. However, this has not been matched with substantial educational resource. As generally argued, there is a wide gap between the policy formulation and implementation. There have been records of some schools marked with overpopulation with students sitting on the windows and some under the trees to receive lessons (Otu, et al., 2011). Again, the aims and objectives of free and compulsory education programme are capable of being achieved if the government adopts more appropriate approaches for improving public enlightenment and social mobilization for community involvement; engage in data collection and analysis; get experts involvement in planning; monitoring and evaluation; prudently handle teacher's recruitment, education, training and retraining and motivating teachers for high productivity; provide infrastructural facilities; enriched curricula; text books and

instructional materials; as well as improving funding and management of the entire process. In the situation where these educational infrastructures became inadequate, such challenges are bound to impede the successful implementation of the programme and its attendant importance to the development of the state.

The pursuit of universal basic education has become of global importance, with free and compulsory education policies serving as cornerstones for increasing access and literacy rates. Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, has embraced this ideal, implementing policies aimed at providing free and compulsory education to its children. (Otu, et al., 2011). The fundamental goal of such initiatives is to break down financial barriers and ensure that all children, irrespective of their socio-economic background, have the opportunity to acquire a foundational education. While these programmes often demonstrate success in boosting enrollment figures, a critical question arises concerning the correlation between increased access and actual student performance in examinations. Udoh (2008) acknowledges that simply providing free and compulsory education may not automatically translate into improved academic outcomes. Numerous other factors, such as the quality of instruction, the availability of adequate learning resources, the learning environment, teacher motivation, and the broader socio-economic background, can significantly influence student achievement. Akwa Ibom State, through its financial policies (Udoh and Madueke, 2018; Udoh, 2022) has made provision for free and compulsory education programme in the state. This research aims to investigate whether the implementation of free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State has a direct and measurable positive impact. It will investigate the various contributing factors that might influence student outcomes, examining whether the policy, in its current form, effectively addresses these crucial elements. By analysing this relationship, the study seeks to provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders, enabling them to refine educational strategies and ensure that increased access to education translates into improved learning outcomes and enhanced academic performance for all students in Akwa Ibom State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Akwa Ibom state government instituted the free and compulsory education policy in the entire state, so as to enable every child to have the opportunity to obtain basic education in the state. This is because the problem of unequal status of parents' access to children's educational achievement and attainment had created serious problems for the economic, social and political development of Akwa Ibom State at large. But despite the implementation of free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State, there remains a significant gap between the policy's intended goals and its actual outcomes in terms of human capital development within the secondary education sector. This discrepancy is evidenced by low enrollment rates, high dropout rates, inadequate infrastructure, low school performance, and suboptimal learning outcomes. The research aims to investigate the factors hindering the effective implementation of free and compulsory education and to identify strategies to enhance its impact on human capital development in selected secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State between 2015 and 2025.

The implementation of free and compulsory education policies has been a global effort aimed at increasing access to education and improving literacy rates. However, the relationship between these policies and student performance in examinations is difficult and with much debate. While free and compulsory education can lead to increased enrollment and

educational attainment, it does not automatically translate into improved student performance in examinations. Several factors can influence this relationship, including, quality of education, socioeconomic factors, infrastructure and resources, teacher quality, assessment and evaluation, cultural and social factors, policy implementation. This study sought to examine the impact of free and compulsory education on students' enrollment in Akwa Ibom State.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following research hypotheses were postulated in Null (Ho) forms for the purpose of statistical conveniences.

Ho: The free and compulsory education tends not to have any impact on students' enrollments in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Education

Education is the process of gaining or sharing knowledge, skills, and character traits. It is also refer to the knowledge and skills gained through study or practice, or the field of study that focuses on teaching methods. Education, according to World Bank (2004), is the process of learning and acquiring knowledge, skills, and values. It encompasses formal learning in schools and universities, as well as informal learning through experiences and interactions. Education plays a crucial role in personal development, societal progress and economic growth

According to Ogunode & Ahaotu (2020), there are three main types of education: formal, informal, and non-formal. Formal education is the traditional type of learning that takes place in schools, colleges, and universities. It follows a structured curriculum and is taught by qualified teachers. Formal education includes several levels. Early childhood education refers to nursery and kindergarten. Primary education takes place in elementary schools. Secondary education includes middle school and high school. Tertiary education refers to college and university studies.

Informal education happens naturally through everyday experiences. It is not planned or structured like formal education. People learn informally by talking with family members, exploring their hobbies and interests, or reading books, magazines, and online content. This type of learning can happen at any time and in any place. Non-formal education is organized learning that happens outside of traditional schools. It often focuses on specific skills or goals and is flexible to meet the learner's needs. Examples of non-formal education include adult education classes, vocational training programs, online courses, and apprenticeships. Funding of education in Nigeria has been problematic over the years. Major reason for the collapsed previous UPE of 1950s and 1976 in Nigeria has been inadequate funding. Also the inability of all the 36 states in Nigeria to implement free/compulsory education had been attributed to lack of funds.

Human Capital Development

According to the postulations of Lawanson, (2009), Human capital development is the process of improving the knowledge, skills, and health of people to help them reach their potential and contribute to society. He also see Human capital development as the strategic approach that involves investing in people through education, health care, nutrition, jobs, and skills. Human capital development (HCD) refers to the process of enhancing the knowledge,

skills, and abilities of individuals within a society or organization, which involves investing in people through various means, including education, training, healthcare, and social programs, to improve their overall productivity and well-being.

Human capital development is crucial for the progress of individuals, communities, and nations. To begin with, a well-educated and skilled workforce is fundamental to boosting economic performance and global competitiveness. It enables industries to grow and economies to thrive, to this, nations that invest in their people are better able to compete in the international market, as human capital is now a major driver of national success.

Recognizing these benefits, the World Bank launched the Human Capital Project in 2017 to encourage global investment in people. As part of this initiative, the Human Capital Index was introduced in 2018 to measure how effectively countries are developing and utilizing their human potential.

Student enrollment

According to Deininger, (2003), Student enrollment is the process of arranging to attend an institution and specific classes. This term also describe the number of students that currently attend a school or a course. Student enrollment refers to the act of signing up for school and/or specific classes or co-curricular activities at that particular school. The enrollment process is completed after a student is granted admission to a particular school. Students can then select courses to take through their school's online student information service.

The author opined that Student enrollment means the process of ensuring attendance in an educational institute and also in specific classes. With this, you can find several students who are currently attending the school or any course. Student enrollment also refers to the act of registering for school, particular classes, or co-curricular activities of any specific school. The term enrollment meaning is the process of officially registering individuals, typically students, to become members or participants of a particular organization, institution, programme, course, or activity. It can further be stated that the process of enrollment is finished once the students are admitted to any specific school or college. The students have the choice to select any course available in the school. Initially, they go through the information service on the web and then go ahead with their selection procedure. A system is set in place by schools, colleges, and other educational institutions to govern the student enrollment process. The schools appoint a team of active and efficient members who have different roles to play, right from advertising on the college website or through a print medium for enrollment in their school, and then invite applications for the same. Next comes the shortlisting of the students according to their merit and profile. This can be done with written exams or their previous year's academic performance.

Student enrollment refers to the formal process by which students register for attendance in educational institutions or programs during an academic period. It acts as a critical indicator of educational demand and plays an essential role in resource allocation, staffing, and funding decisions for schools and governments (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2021). Enrollment can be classified into initial enrollment, where students register for the first time, and re-enrollment, where existing students continue their studies in subsequent terms. Furthermore, students may enroll either full-time or part-time, depending on their course load (OECD, 2023).

Several factors affect students enrollment levels, including; Demographic trends such

as population growth or decline directly influence the number of potential students eligible to enroll (World Bank, 2022). Economic factors, including household income and affordability of education, significantly impact enrollment rates, with higher income generally correlating with increased access to schooling (OECD, 2023). Additionally, education policies, such as compulsory education laws and the provision of scholarships, encourage higher enrollment (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2021). Social and cultural norms, including gender roles and parental education levels, also affect participation in education, alongside the reputation and perceived quality of educational institutions (Tinto, 1993). Access-related issues, such as the availability of schools and transportation, further determine enrollment figures (World Bank, 2022). Moreover, external factors like pandemics or political unrest may cause temporary or longer-term disruptions in student enrollment patterns (OECD, 2023).

Again, accurate Student enrollment data helps institutions effectively manage resources. By understanding the size of the student body, schools can better allocate staff, schedule classroom use, and prepare necessary teaching materials (Smith & Jones, 2020). Student Enrollment systems support student diversity, allowing institutions to bring together learners from various cultural, social, and economic backgrounds. This diversity enriches the educational experience by promoting the exchange of different perspectives and fostering a more inclusive learning environment (Anderson, 2018).

Free and Compulsory Education and Students Enrollment

World Bank (2004) Education Development goals state that education is developing. It created choices and opportunities for people, reduced the burden of poverty and diseases and gave a strong virile in the society. For nations, it created a dynamic workforce and well informed citizens able to compete and co-operate globally and opening the door to economic-social prosperity. The world conference of education for all realized that the need for UPE had been the world's greatest challenge in the history of education. World Bank (1990) Ultimate goal were to provide the basic needs which consisted of knowledge, skills attitudes and values upon which individual could build their lives if they did not receive more formal education. These basic learning needs enable the individuals the ability to read and write, to work with numbers, adapting to change of culture social and economic life of their community, their nation and the world. Therefore primary education could be said to be the most universal and significant level of formal education where most pupils could be said to be most universal and significant level of formal education where most pupils should get schooling. In Akwa Ibom State, girls' child education has improved since the free and compulsory education (Peters, Bassey, and Usoro, 2020)

Statistics from World Bank (2000) showed that despite this much effort on EFA, about 115 million school-age children were not in school. Graham-Brown (1991) observed that by 1980's the growth in education had slowed down in some countries being reversed. The article further recorded that in low income countries less than two – thirds of those who enrolled in primary school completed the entire cycle this proportion had been declining in the recent years. Despite the efforts of the UN charter and world education conferences the goals to achieve by 2005 and Education for all by 2015 may be a mirage especially in some less developed countries. United Nations International Children Education Fund (UNICEF, 1990) stated that Africa was one of the regions in the world where primary education status declined in 1950's. The same report showed that the Gross enrollment growth declined by 7 percent between 1975 and 1980 and by 20 percent in 1980 to 1990. By 1993 the net primary school enrolment in sub-Saharan Africa was 40 percent.

Free Compulsory Education and Human Capital Development

People are a fundamental component with any successfully developing organization. Take away the people and the organization is nothing. Take away peoples motivation, commitment and ability to work together in well-organized teams, and again, the organization is nothing. Conversely, inspire the people to work well, creatively, productively, and the organization can fly. Logically therefore the development and proper utilization of people are vital to the success of all quality management initiatives (Republic of Nigeria, 1999). As a result of the free primary education, the situation of the teaching force in most of the local governments in Akwa Ibom Sate Government is generally bad. Teachers complain of increased pupil teacher ratios. Many primary schools are understaffed as a result of the free primary education program. This does not augur well for the quality of education being delivered. Many school management committees are opinion that as a result of the ban levies, they are unable to recruit extra teachers through PTA and this has also seriously affected the pre-schools units' (Salami, 2014). The study by Action aid (2007) cites lack of teachers to handle the large number of pupils in FCE program. The number of teachers since 1998 has remained the same. This has been attributed to the government's inability to hire more teachers due to world Banks IMF ceiling to hiring of more teachers. The impact of this to the pupil teacher ratio (PTR) in public primary schools has seen teachers unable to handle the large number of pupils under them (Todley, 2005).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Human Capital Theory propounded by Theodore Schultz in 1961

The Human Capital Theory propounded by Theodore Schultz in 1961 the theory states that education. Education should be viewed as an investment good. The investment in education is likened to the accumulation of human capital with a view to receive a higher income afterwards. Since education is an investment good, there is both a demand and supply implications. The demand for education is determined by equating the marginal cost of education (consisting of direct cost, like tuition fees, and opportunity cost arising from foregone income) to the marginal benefits due to a higher present value of lifetime income. As expected, the demand for education depends negatively on the interest rate and both direct and indirect cost.

The higher marginal cost of education relative to the marginal benefit, the lower will be the demand for education. Since education is affected by the cost (in this case the price), then it follows that education is affected by wealth. However, noted that while initial wealth has no impact on the decision on receiving education under perfect information, the corresponding demand elasticity is positive under uncertainty about future wage rates. A positive impact of wealth on the demand for education also occurs if individuals are liquidity constrained.

Also, education can be viewed as a consumption good. It therefore follows that there is an observable positive income effect with respect to the demand for education. A high demand for education can also signal a high productivity to potential employers. The main idea starts from the premise that firms cannot observe the productivity of their workers directly. At the firm level, educated individuals are more likely to choose input combinations that minimizes cost; and in the household production, there is bound to be a rising productivity.

Human capital theory posits that individuals invest in their education, training, and

skills to increase their productivity and earning potential as human capital theory remains a valuable framework for understanding the relationship between education, training, and economic outcomes. As the world continues to evolve, the importance of investing in human capital will only grow.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the survey and descriptive analysis design. The study population for the study was 461,615, being the total number students' enrolled for free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom state (2015-2025) (Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board) This research adopted the Taro Yamani Formula as the sampling technique in determining the sampling size, and the sample size = 400 approximately. The purposive sampling procedure was adopted for this research.

Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics analysis, through the use of tables, frequency and percentage. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson product-moment correlation to determine the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

The decision rule used in this study is stated thus: Reject the null hypotheses if the probability value (p-value) is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). Alternatively, accept the null hypotheses if the probability value (p-value) is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). This can be stated symbolically as: Accept H_0 if $P_c < P_t$, Reject H_0 if $P_c > P_t$.

RESULTS

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between free and compulsory education on students enrollment in Akwa Ibom State.

Tables 1: Responses on the relationship between free and compulsory education and students' enrollment in Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Free and Compulsory Education and Students Enrollment	S/A	A	D	S/D	TOTAL (%)
1.	The free and compulsory education brings about increase in number of students in classes in your school	250 (75%)	50 (25%)	-	-	300 (100%)
2	The free and compulsory education programme is affordable for the common man to train his children	290 (95%)	10 (5%)	-	-	300 (100%)
3	The free and compulsory education programme has provided out of school children to return back to school	320 (60%)	80 (40%)	-	-	300 (100%)
4	The free and compulsory education programme has enhanced students overall population in your school	280 (90%)	20 (10%)	-	-	300 (100%)

Source: Researcher's conceptualization (2026)

From the questionnaire retrieved, it was observed that free and compulsory education brings about increase in number of students, affordability for the common man to train his children, out of school children to return back to school, enhancement of students overall population in Government primary school

Test of Hypotheses

The Null hypothesis indicates that there is no significant relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and regression analysis was used in analysis of the above hypothesis with the examination of the responses to the questions on the relationship between free and compulsory education on students enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. The PPMC obtained for each of the responses to the questions is presented below.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients for Hypothesis One

		Students enrolment	Students enrolment	Students enrolment	Students enrolment
free and compulsory education 1	Pearson Correlation	1	.593**	.414**	.426**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	300	300	300	300
free and compulsory education s 2	Pearson Correlation	.593**	1	.659**	.599**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	300	250	300	300
free and compulsory education 3	Pearson Correlation	.414**	.659**	1	.932**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	300	300	300	300
free and compulsory education 4	Pearson Correlation	.426**	.599**	.932**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	300	300	300	300

Source: Researcher's Computation (2026)

Table 2 indicates that on the statements that there is no significant relationship between significant relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. Pearson Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficients generated include 0.893, 0.414, 0.426, 0.659, 0.599, and 0.932 were found to be statistically significant at 5% level of significance. This is an indication of the significant relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. However, on the nature and degree of relationship between free and compulsory education (independent variable) and student's enrollment (Dependent Variable), the regression and correlation results are presented below.

Table 3: Analysis Results for Hypothesis One

FCE= 4.446 + 0.091	SE
T-stat= (51.795)	(4.244)
Prob. = (0.000)	(0.026)
R= 0.141; R ² = 0.020; F-stat= 5.035; Prob. (F-stat) = 0.076	

Source: Researcher's Computation (2026)

Table 3 shows that student's enrollment (SE) will remain positive at an average of 4.446 units, if there are no changes in free and compulsory education (FCE). This implies that free and compulsory education (FCE) remain constant, indicating the more the unit of free and compulsory education the more the level of student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State which will lead to an increase of 0.091 units change. This positive relationship is statistically significant with a computed t-statistic value of 4.244 and a probability value of 0.076 (Sig = 0.026), since the probability value obtained is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance.

The correlation (PPMC) coefficient R-value of 0.141 indicates the existence of a positive correlation between free and compulsory education (FCE) and student's enrollment (SE). However, this can be said to be a high positive correlation. Also, the predictive power of free and compulsory education (FCE) to explain the changes in student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State (SE), is high given the obtained coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.020 obtained.

Finally, given that the computed F-statistic value obtained is 5.035 and the probability (sig) value is 0.026, the relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State, can be said to have goodness-of-fit. This implies that the relationship is statistically significant. This is an indication that the null hypothesis earlier stated will fail to hold, and is hereby rejected. This implies that a positive and significant relationship exists between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Free and Compulsory Education on Students Enrollment

The findings on the statements that there is no significant relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. Pearson Moment Correlation (PPMC) coefficients generated include 0.893, 0.414, 0.426, 0.659, 0.599, and 0.932 were found to be statistically significant at 5% level of significance. This is an indication of the significant relationship between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. Further findings shows that student's enrollment (SE) will remain positive at an average of 4.446 units, if there are no changes in free and compulsory education (FCE). This implies that free and compulsory education (FCE) remain constant, indicating the more the unit of free and compulsory education the more the level of student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State which will lead to an increase of 0.091 units change. This positive relationship is statistically significant with a computed t-statistic value of 4.244 and a probability value of 0.076 (Sig = 0.026), since the probability value obtained is less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance.

The correlation (PPMC) coefficient R-value of 0.141 indicates the existence of a positive correlation between free and compulsory education (FCE) and student's enrollment

(SE). This implies that a positive and significant relationship exists between free and compulsory education and student's enrollment in Akwa Ibom State

CONCLUSION

This study was an examination of impact of free and compulsory education on school enrollment in selected secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State between 2015 and 2025. The objectives developed in the study were to find out the impact of free and compulsory education on students enrollment in Akwa Ibom State. Survey method and descriptive research design was adopted in the study. After careful data analysis, it was concluded that the free and compulsory education of the Akwa Ibom State Government had great impact the young population of the state which translated into school enrollment in the state. This was an indication of the facts found through data was collected using research questionnaire which was administered to a sample of 400 respondents in Akwa Ibom State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made for the study that:

1. The Akwa Ibom State Government should work hand in hand with different ministry of education in formulating policies to encourage more students' enrollment.
2. The Akwa Ibom State Government should collaborate with educational agencies and civil societies in strengthening the free and compulsory education in Akwa Ibom State.

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